

Shared Memories, Identity Fusion, and Morality

1. Background

The present work has two goals¹: to investigate the psychological impact of a shared dysphoric experience on group cohesion and to examine the relationships between group cohesion and morality. Both objectives aim to tackle the differences between two forms of group cohesion: identity fusion (Swann, Gómez, Seyle, Morales & Huici, 2009), which has been linked to dysphoric experiences, and social identification (Tajfel & Turner, 1979), thought to result from shared identity markers acquired via social learning (Whitehouse & Lanman, 2014). As an example of a shared dysphoric event we chose to focus on the terrorist attack that hit Kuta (Bali, Indonesia) in 2002 and its effect on group cohesion among local Balinese Hindus.

Goal 1. Previous research suggests that visceral and emotional memories of a dysphoric event that are highly transformative for personal identity are a powerful engine for fusion – but not for identification – when they are perceived to be shared with other group members (Whitehouse et al., 2014, Whitehouse et al., 2017; Muzzulini, Kapitany, van Mulukom & Whitehouse, submitted). We refer to experiences of this type as *imagistic experiences* (Whitehouse, 2004). The extent to which imagistic experiences need to be undergone by group members at the same time and place to generate identity fusion with a group, however, has not been fully investigated. In this study, we compare the effects of direct, staggered, and vicarious imagistic experiences on the formation of fusion (vs. identification) through processes of perceived and evident sharedness, group consequentiality, personal identity transformativeness, and memory visceralness.

Goal 2. The relationship between fusion, identification, and moral concerns is also an understudied topic. We will conduct exploratory analyses of the relationships between fusion, identification and a set of moral domains identified by the theory of Morality as Cooperation or ‘MAC’ (Curry, Chesters, & Van Lissa, 2019). The MAC framework predicts that the following seven cooperative rules will be judged morally good in all human societies: help your group, help your family, return favours, be brave, defer to superiors, divide resources fairly, respect others' property (Curry, Mullins, & Whitehouse, 2019).

¹ The objectives reported below cover two related yet separate research questions. For this reason, we may report the results across two separate papers.

2. Participants

Participants are Balinese Hindus whose memory representations differ according to the mode of experience of the event. We aim to recruit 200 people who experienced the attack at close quarters, as it was happening (the *direct* condition); 200 people who learned about the news of the attack from another location and/or at different times (the *staggered* condition); and 200 people who have no experience of the event but yet learned about it through the story telling of another person who had a direct experience (the *vicarious* condition). In the vicarious condition, we may also include younger participants (i.e., aged under 35) and then control for age in subsequential analyses. The inclusion criteria for each condition are reported across the table below.

Criteria	Group		
	DIRECT	STAGGERED	VICARIOUS
Mode of experience	Participant could either 1) hear the bombing; 2) witness the bombing in person; 3) survive the bombing.	Participant first learned about the event from either 1) seeing it reported in the media 2) hearing about it from another person (who did not have direct experience).	Participant first learned about the bombing by hearing the eyewitness testimony of someone who had a direct experience of the bombing.
	Participant was in Kuta, Bali during the bombing	Participant was not in Kuta during the bombing	Participant currently live in Kuta or surroundings
Memory representation	Memory of the event as experienced	Memory of how the news was first learned	Memory of a witness' testimony of the event
Age	> 35 years-old	> 35 years-old	> 18 years-old
Religion	Hindu	Hindu	Hindu
Sample size	N = 200	N = 200	N = 200
Education	High school diploma and above	High school diploma and above	High school diploma and above

3. Measures

Memory Recall		
<i>Narrative</i>	<p><i>Direct:</i> In this section, we will ask you to think about your personal experience of the Bali bombing. We would appreciate your providing some details about your experience. For example, where exactly were you, who else was involved, and what were you thinking and feeling? Also, please say a word or two about what this event might mean for who you are as a Balinese Hindu.</p> <p><i>Staggered:</i> In this section, we will ask you to think about how you first learned the news of the Bali bombing. We would appreciate your providing some details about your experience. For example, where exactly were you, who else was involved, and what were you thinking and feeling? Also, please say a word or two about what this event might mean for who you are as a Balinese Hindu.</p> <p><i>Vicarious:</i> In this section, we will ask you to focus on somebody else’s personal experience of the Bali bombing. We will refer to this person as the storyteller. The storyteller could be a friend, a family member, or an acquaintance of yours who has shared her/his personal memories of the Bali bombing with you. If you know more than one person who experienced the Bali bombing, please choose the experience that is most significant for you personally. Please think back to the story teller’s memory of the Bali bombing. We would appreciate your providing some details about the storyteller experience. For example, where exactly was the storyteller, who else was involved, and what was the storyteller thinking and feeling? Also, please say a word or two about what this event might mean for the storyteller as a Balinese Hindu.</p>	
<i>Vividness</i>	How vivid is this memory in your mind?	1 – 6
<i>Emotional arousal</i>	<p>Intensity – How intense are the emotions you associate to this memory?</p> <p>Valence – How negative/positive are the emotions you associate to this memory?</p>	1 – 6

<i>Visceral response</i>	4 items, Talarico & Rubin, 2003	1 – 6
Personal identity and appraisals of the event		
<i>Personal identity Transformativeness</i>	3 items from Berntsen & Rubin, 2006	1 – 6
<i>Consequentiality</i>	How consequential is the Bali bombing for you and other Balinese Hindus? How important is the Bali bombing in defining ‘who we are’ as Balinese Hindus?	1 – 6
<i>Event opaqueness</i>	To what extent do you think that the Bali bombers had a clear purpose in carrying out the attack? Do you think that the bombing has caused Balinese Hindus to think more about the meaning of life?	1 – 6
Sharedness with the group		
<i>Co-presents / Storyteller</i>	Who was with you when you first learned about the news of the Bali bombing?	Open question
<i>Relation with Co-presents / Storyteller</i>	Indicate who the [co-present/storyteller] is in relation to you by ticking one or more options below. (e.g., a friend, a family member, etc.)	Multiple answer
<i>Evident sharedness</i>	Are you assuming that those people were there, or do you actually remember those people being there? How vivid is the image of these people in your mind?	1=I just assume those people were there, 6=I remember the presence of those exact people 1 – 6
<i>Perceived sharedness</i>	To what extent do you think that [the co-presents / the storyteller] share the same experience and memories of the Bali bombing? To what extent do you think that you and other Balinese Hindus share the same experience and memories of the Bali bombing?	1 – 6
Group cohesion		
<i>Targets</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Family - Co-presents / Storyteller - The victims of the bombing - Other Balinese Hindus - Other Indonesians 	
<i>Identity fusion</i>	Pictorial scale, Swann et al., 2009	1 – 7
<i>Social identification</i>	1 item, Postmes et al., 2013	1 – 6

Moral domains		
<i>Participants' perspective</i>	‘Do you think that the Bali bombing was morally bad or morally good?’	1 – 6
	‘Please tell us how relevant each type of action is to you personally’. Followed by MAC-Q, Curry, Chesters, & van Lissa, 2019	1 – 6
<i>Group perspective</i>	‘Do you think that the Bali bombing was morally bad or morally good to other Balinese Hindus?’	1 – 6
	‘Tell us to what extent you think that other Balinese Hindus pride themselves on the following actions.’ Followed by MAC-Q, Curry et al., 2019	1 – 6
<i>Moral violation of the bombing</i>	‘When you think about why the bombers did what they did, to what extent are the following considerations relevant to you?’ Followed by MAC-Q, Curry et al., 2019 (short version)	1 – 6
<i>Ranking of the most violated domain</i>	‘In judging the actions of the Bali bombers, which ONE of these considerations is the most important? The Bali bombers...’ Followed by MAC-Q, Curry et al., 2019 (short version)	Ranking task

4. Pre-registered Hypotheses

Goal 1

H1. We expect to observe a variation in scores of identity fusion according to the directedness and imagistic properties of the experience.

H1.1. Participants in the direct condition will score higher than participants in the staggered and vicarious conditions across all fusion targets.

H1.2. Within each condition, participants will score higher on fusion targets when:

- They learned/experienced the event in the presence of members of the ingroup target;
- They have an episodic-like recall of those group members being present (for the vicarious condition, of the storyteller sharing their memory)
- There are strong relational ties with those who were co-present (for the vicarious condition, with the storyteller);

H1.3. Higher levels of fusion with all target groups will be associated with higher scores on memory's visceralness, emotional arousal, and personal identity transformativeness across all conditions.

H2. Scores of identity fusion will be shaped by the effects of 1) memory recall, 2) personal identity transformativeness and 3) perceived sharedness.

Based on previous research, we predict the following relationships among variables:

H2.1 – Memory recall (i.e., viscerality, vividness, and emotional intensity associated to the memory) positively predicts personal identity transformativeness.

H2.2 – The relationship between transformativeness and fusion with relevant targets is mediated by perceived sharedness (matched with respective fusion targets).

H2.3 – The pathway highlighted in H3 will be weaker in predicting group identification.

Goal 2

As there is currently not enough previous evidence to justify strong predictions, we will present only one directional hypothesis associated with fusion (see point H3 below). Other hypotheses are theoretically motivated but have not yet been tested in the empirical literature, hence we include them under the exploratory analyses. We will report the findings and relate them to the hypotheses specified but may place them within supplementary materials.

H3. We predict that the differences in the type of bonds formed through fusion and identification will also impact moral reasoning in distinctive ways. Specifically, since fusion is associated with perceptions of familial ties and psychological kinship whereas identification focuses on categorical group identities and extra-familial relationships, we expect fusion to display a stronger association with moral commitments to kin altruism and group loyalty in all cases. Also, since fusion is strongly associated with self-sacrifice for the group and especially the willingness to fight and die to protect group members, we predict a strong relationship between fusion and heroism. The differences will be in the *relative strength* of the relationship between each domain and fusion and identification.

5. Exploratory analyses

Goal 1

EXP1. The relationship between consequentiality and memory recall is moderated by the directedness of experience, i.e., consequentiality of direct experiences has a stronger effect than staggered and vicarious experiences.

EXP2. The relationship between transformativeness and perception of sharedness is moderated by the evidence of sharedness, i.e., stronger evidence of being co-present is associated with a stronger effect of transformativeness and perceived sharedness on fusion.

EXP3. We will test our model controlling for event opaqueness.

EXP4. We will explore the factors that contribute to fusion with the storyteller in the vicarious condition. For example, does the storyteller's greater involvement in the Bali bombing predict greater fusion? Does greater frequency of memory recall and the emotional tone of the narrative predict greater fusion? Is the story told in vivid experiential details that lead to fusion with the storyteller or vice versa? Within EXP4, we will also test whether stronger fusion with the storyteller is associated with 1) stronger fusion with an extended target such as the victims of the bombing and other Balinese Hindus and 2) greater willingness to pass the story down the new generations.

EXP5. We will score the memory narrative according to their emotional tone (and other post-hoc indices, if any) and assess their associations with fusion.

EXP6. According to our theoretical framework, shared experiences that form part of both the essential autobiographical and the group give rise to identity fusion. While we hypothesise that this would be more likely to occur in the direct condition, it is possible that it occurs to some extent also in the staggered or vicarious conditions. Therefore, with all three kinds of experiences we will investigate key mediators between shared experience and identity fusion, including consequentiality, sharedness, and transformativeness.

Goal 2

EXP7. We will examine the relationships between fusion, identification, subjective-MAC and group-MAC whereby the latter reflect one's personal and group identity respectively. In light of the fusion framework, we could anticipate that highly fused participants will show a strong correlation between subjective-MAC and group-MAC, at least with regard to the group's most sacred moral norms. On the other hand, if fusion to the group does not entail fusion to a set of group-MAC sacred values, we may expect fusion with the group to predict a preference for kin altruism, group loyalty, and heroism to the relative detriment of other group-MAC domains. However, we could also anticipate a strong correlation between the subjective-MAC and the group-MAC among highly identified participants irrespective of whether any of the group-MAC domains are 'sacralised'. This may be explained by the fact that identification may be more strongly related to endorsement of group norms than fusion. In fact, it may be the case that highly identified participants will personally endorse whatever moral norm they think the group favours, because these norms are socially learned. It may therefore emerge that *both* fusion and identification show high correlation with subjective-MAC and group-MAC but that the pathway to reach such outcome is different. For these reasons and because the topic is undetermined by existing data, we will explore the relationships and report on the respective results in order to better inform hypothesis generating in future research.

EXP8. We will examine whether and how fusion and identification explain variations among participants' judgment of what moral domains the bombing impacted. Stemming from the idea that fusion implies familial ties and psychological kinship, we expect that highly fused individuals will be mostly outraged by actions that may have harmed peoples' families and communities.

EXP9. We will examine whether and how directedness of experience variations in people's moral reasoning.